

Imaginary Coupling Constants and Minimizing the Laws of Nature - 8T

O Manor

August 7, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the two main equations of the 8T and in particular by constructing situations in which only two distinct couplings are presented on the metric tensor M , we can reach net curvature averages, which can be classified as a pseudo- interaction for those who do not know the primordial coupling series. Additional take provided on additional Lagrangian oriented feature of a final theory, which is to minimize the number of laws that govern nature.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equation (1.2). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. Suppose the metric tensor has two interactions on it, which are studied by an observer. This observer does not know that the Bosons are isomorphic to the prime ring, and there are only two interactions, the electric interaction and the fourth interaction.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7$$

Assuming the net curvature appear not in a superposition but rather as distinct propagations on the metric tensor. If the observer is not familiar with the series, he could for example take the average of the two net curvature as a new coupling term. That is, associate Bosons to the ring of the integers and not to the ring of the primes, in that case to the integer six, the average. He could decide that there is a coupling constant, whose magnitude lies in between the range r :

$$128 < r < 850$$

$$\frac{\gamma + 7}{2} = 6$$

While in fact, he is measuring the average net curvature of two distinct prime amounts of net curvature. That is somewhat resembles the pseudo-forces measured from certain frames of reference in Einstein theory of relativity. We previously stated that in the 8T, the coupling magnitudes are invariant as the prime ring itself is observer invariant. It is also invariant across the manifold packet, different universe will possess the same coupling magnitudes, and as a result the same particles. That is due of the invariance of the prime ring. We can not associate a Boson to an even number, which vanish. In that sense it is imaginary.

Minimizing the Laws

The last part of this paper will revolve around a feature of nature which was mentioned briefly in previous papers, and in the 8T thesis. Lagrangian oriented theories are based upon the principle of least action, which deals with minima of certain classes, and this is the most significant feature of those theories. There is one additional minima in the 8T and in a final theory that should get our attention, as it is just as important. That is minimizing the number of laws that govern everything. In every universe, at every stage of development of the manifold, from the flattening by the packet to complete coldness, the number of laws should stand at minima. In other words, the number of equations or ideas in which we use to describe everything should be minimal, and that is a significant feature of a final theory. The minima is not only path-oriented such as in classical mechanics or QED, it is also manifested in the number of laws. 8T is that kind of theory as all we have achieved, from dark energy to the coupling series and the Quark masses series, is encompassed in just one equation and two conditions.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

In addition, all the standard model of particle physics is encompassed in just two conditions. For fermions:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

Bosons as net curvature of discrete prime amounts:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)